

Abstract

Proposal of psychological intervention for the emotional regulation of the students of the University of Sonora

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Abstract: According to the World Health Organization [1] the prevalence of mental disorders has increased. In Mexico, this situation is no different, due to the increase in the trend of suicide cases, locating the highest rate in the population of young people between 18 and 29 years of age [2]. Despite the fact that Sonora is above the average in the affective balance of the National Self-Informed Well-being Survey [3], it is in fourth place in the country with the highest rate of self-inflicted injuries. This is the context in which the student body at the University of Sonora is immersed, in addition to the stressors produced by the COVID-19 pandemic, academic stress, among others related to the role as a student. The continuous exposure to these stressful situations can affect the well-being and mental health of the students, as well as the perception of self-efficacy, self-esteem and motivation. Emotional regulation is a psychological process that could help them effectively cope with stressful situations and appropriately achieve their academic goals, therefore, exacerbations based on emotional regulation strategies can be an effective strategy for preventing the negative effects of stress from academic and a skill that promotes the mental health of students. To this end, it is proposed to evaluate and implement a model of brief psychological intervention with individual and group modality, despite the demand and possible effectiveness of the care model, the coverage issue remains under discussion, so it is concluded to continue exploring care strategies

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